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Design and operation of multiport converters for distribution systems

REPORT

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Resum

Els sistemes de distribució d'energia elèctrica estan experimentant un augment de la integració d'energies renovables, que està invertint el flux d'energia durant alguns períodes i modificant el seu funcionament convencional. En aquest context, cal fer reducció de la generació distribuïda renovable per tenir en compte les limitacions elèctriques dels transformadors i línies, que són principalment les desviacions de tensió i les sobrecàrregues de potència. Els convertidors multiport (MPC) amb emmagatzematge d'energia es presenten com una solució potencial per millorar el funcionament del flux d'energia al sistema de distribució i minimitzar la reducció de generació renovable. Alternativament també es pot considerar afegir sistemes d'emmagatzematge d'energia, interruptors i noves línies.

Aquest Treball de Fi de Màster presenta una metodologia basada en l'optimització per dimensionar convertidors multiport. La metodologia es divideix en tres passos: selecció de dies dels perfils de càrrega i disponibilitat de recursos renovables, dimensionament de l'emmagatzematge i optimització de les dimensions del convertidor multiport. L'optimització de les dimensions del MPC considera els dies seleccionats anteriorment en lloc de tot l'any, inclou les limitacions elèctriques i també optimitza el funcionament del sistema. Aquesta metodologia també proporciona indicadors tècnics i econòmics per a una avaluació completa de la integració del convertidor multiport.

La metodologia general s'avalua en un cas d'estudi basat en una xarxa de referència de mitja tensió del CIGRE. La solució del convertidor multiport es compara amb configuracions alternatives amb bateries separades i una interconnexió simple d'interruptors, també té en compte diferents penetracions d'energia renovable. Així mateix, es realitza una anàlisi de sensibilitat dels paràmetres econòmics sobre l'optimització. En general, l'objectiu és identificar els millors escenaris on els convertidors multiport es poden considerar una solució potencial.

Els resultats conclouen que la potència nominal dels terminals convertidors multiport utilitzats per intercanviar potència entre diferents alimentadors es dimensiona com la potència nominal de les línies i transformadors en escenaris amb generació distribuïda desequilibrada als alimentadors. Mentre que en escenaris amb generació distribuïda equilibrada, la mida de la potència nominal dels terminals del convertidor multiport és menor i té més variabilitat. Com a conclusió general, els resultats mostren que el convertidor multiport pot reduir la reducció de la generació en termes equivalents o fins i tot millor que les solucions de bateries, especialment en escenaris amb generació distribuïda desequilibrada als alimentadors. Amb una alta penetració de renovables, tots els escenaris estudiats són econòmicament factibles per instal·lar un convertidor multiport. Els escenaris amb generació desequilibrada són factibles si es redueix la capacitat de generació renovable, tret que les bateries dels alimentadors estiguin inicialment instal·lades. En general, per a tots els escenaris, un convertidor multiport amb una bateria centralitzada és la millor opció.

Resumen

Los sistemas de distribución de energía eléctrica están experimentando un aumento de la integración de energías renovables, lo que está invirtiendo el flujo de energía durante algunos periodos y modificando su funcionamiento convencional. En este contexto, la reducción de la generación distribuida renovable es necesario para considerar las limitaciones eléctricas de transformadores y líneas, que son principalmente desviaciones de tensión y sobrecargas de potencia. Los convertidores multipuerto (MPC) con almacenamiento de energía se presentan como una solución potencial para mejorar la operación del flujo de energía en el sistema de distribución y minimizar la reducción de generación renovable. Alternativamente también se puede considerar añadir sistemas de almacenamiento de energía, interruptores y nuevas líneas.

Este Trabajo de Fin de Máster presenta una metodología basada en la optimización para dimensionar convertidores multipuerto. La metodología se divide en tres pasos: selección de días de los perfiles de carga y disponibilidad de recursos renovables, dimensionamiento del almacenamiento y optimización del dimensionamiento del convertidor multipuerto. La optimización del dimensionamiento del MPC considera los días seleccionados previamente en lugar de todo el año, incluye restricciones eléctricas y también optimiza la operación del sistema. Esta metodología también proporciona indicadores técnicos y económicos para una evaluación completa de la integración del convertidor multipuerto.

La metodología general se evalúa en un caso de estudio basado en una red de referencia de media tensión de CIGRE. La solución del convertidor multipuerto se compara con configuraciones alternativas con baterías separadas y una interconexión de interruptor simple, también considera diferentes penetraciones de energía renovable. Además, se realiza un análisis de sensibilidad de los parámetros económicos sobre la optimización. En general, el objetivo es identificar los mejores escenarios en los que los convertidores multipuerto pueden considerarse como una solución potencial.

Los resultados concluyen que la potencia nominal de los terminales del convertidor multipuerto utilizado para el intercambio de energía entre diferentes alimentadores se dimensiona como la potencia nominal de las líneas y transformadores en escenarios con generación distribuida desequilibrada en los alimentadores. Mientras que en escenarios de generación distribuida equilibrada, el tamaño de la potencia nominal de los terminales del convertidor multipuerto es menor y tiene más variabilidad. Como conclusión general, los resultados muestran que el convertidor multipuerto puede reducir la reducción de generación en términos equivalentes o incluso mejor que las soluciones de baterías, especialmente en escenarios con generación distribuida desequilibrada en los alimentadores. Con alta penetración de renovables, todos los escenarios estudiados son económicamente viables para instalar un convertidor multipuerto. Los escenarios con generación desequilibrada siguen siendo viables si se reduce la capacidad de generación renovable, a menos que las baterías de los alimentadores estén inicialmente instaladas. En general, para todos los escenarios, un convertidor multipuerto con batería centralizada es la mejor opción.

Abstract

Electrical power distribution systems are experiencing an increase in renewable energy integration, which is reversing the power flow during some periods and modifying their conventional operation. In this context, the curtailment of renewable distributed generation is needed to consider the electrical limitations of transformers and lines, which are mainly voltage deviations and power overloads. Multiport converters (MPC) with energy storage are presented as a potential solution for enhancing power flow operation in the distribution system and minimizing renewable generation curtailments. Alternatively, adding energy storage systems (ESS), switches, soft open points, and new lines can also be considered.

This Master's Thesis presents an optimisation-based methodology to size multiport power converters. The methodology is divided into three steps: days selection of the load and renewable resource availability profiles, storage sizing, and multiport converter sizing optimisation. The MPC sizing optimisation considers the days selected previously instead of the whole year, includes electrical constraints, and also optimises the system operation. This methodology also provides technical and economic indicators for a complete evaluation of the multiport converter integration.

The general methodology is evaluated in a case study based on a medium voltage benchmark network from CIGRE. The multiport converter solution is compared to alternative configurations with separated batteries and a simple switch interconnection, it also considers different penetrations of renewable energy. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis of economic parameters is performed on the optimisation. Overall, the objective is to identify the best scenarios where multiport converters can be considered as a potential solution.

The results conclude that the rated power of the multiport converter terminals used to exchange power between different feeders is sized as the nominal power of the lines and transformers in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders. Whereas in scenarios with balanced distributed generation, the size of the rated power of the multiport converter terminals is lower and has more variability. As a general conclusion, the results show that the multiport converter can reduce power curtailment in equivalent terms or even better than battery solutions, especially in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders. With high penetration of renewables, all scenarios studied are economically feasible to install a multiport converter. Scenarios with unbalanced generation remain feasible if the renewable generation capacity is reduced, unless batteries are initially installed in the feeders. In general, for all scenarios, a multiport converter with a centralised battery is the best option.

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Glossary

Acronyms

AC	Alternating current
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
DC	Direct current
DER	Distributed energy resources
ESS	Energy storage systems
LP	Linear programming
LV	Low voltage
MINLP	Mixed-integer non-linear programming
MIP	Mixed-integer programming
MPC	Multiport Converter
MV	Medium voltage
NLP	Nonlinear programming
OPF	Optimal power flow
PF	Power flow
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable energy sources
SOC	State of Charge of the battery
SOP	Soft Open Point
SST	Solid State Transformers
VSC	Voltage Source Converters

Parameters

ΔC_{cap}	Variation of the battery cost in [%]
ΔC_{conv}	Variation of the converter cost in [%]
ΔPBT	Variation of the payback time respect to Ref in [%]

- Δt Time-step of the model in [h]
- $\delta_{y_{i,k}}$ Admittance phase of the line between nodes i, k in [$^{\circ}$]
- $\delta_{z_{i,k}}$ Impedance phase of the line between nodes i, k in [$^{\circ}$]
- η_{char} Charging efficiency of the battery in [p.u.]
- η_{disch} Discharging efficiency of the battery in [p.u.]
- τ_{bat} Energy loss ratio of the battery in [p.u.]
- $B_{i,k}$ Imaginary part of the Y_{bus} matrix at nodes i, k in [p.u.]
- C_{cap} Energy storage cost in [€/kWh]
- C_{conv-k} Unitary cost of the multiport converter terminal k in [€/kVA]
- C_{conv} Converter cost in [€/kVA]
- C_{en} Average annual energy price in [€/kWh]
- $E_{cap-b,i}$ Energy storage capacity of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- E_{ren-bc} Annual renewable generation in the base configuration in [kWh]
- $E_{ren-max}$ Annual renewable energy available in [kWh]
- $G_{i,k}$ Real part of the Y_{bus} matrix at nodes i, k in [p.u.]
- $i_{max,MPC-k,i}$ Maximum current of the multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- $i_{max-b,i}$ Maximum current of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- $i_{max-g,i}$ Maximum current of the generator g connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- $i_{max-i,k}$ Maximum current magnitude of the line between nodes i, k in [p.u.]
- $p_{max-g,i,t,d}$ Maximum available power from the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]
- $p_{n-b,i}$ Nominal active power of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- $p_{n-g,i}$ Nominal active power of the generator g connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- $PF_{b,i}$ Power factor of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- $PF_{g,i}$ Power factor of the generator g connected to the node i in [p.u.]
- S_b Base power of the system in [kW]
- $s_{max-b,m}$ Maximum apparent power of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]

$s_{max-g,m}$ Maximum apparent power of the generator g connected to the node i in [p.u.]

$SOC_{max-b,i}$ Maximum state of charge of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]

$SOC_{min-b,i}$ Minimum state of charge of the battery b connected to the node i in [p.u.]

$v_{max,i}$ Maximum voltage magnitude value of node i , supposed as 1.1 p.u.

$v_{min,i}$ Minimum voltage magnitude value of node i , supposed as 0.9 p.u.

v_{n-i} Nominal voltage magnitude of the node i in [p.u.]

w_d Weight of the representative day d in the year

$y_{i,k}$ Admittance magnitude of the line between nodes i, k in [p.u.]

$z_{i,k}$ Impedance magnitude of the line between nodes i, k in [p.u.]

Variables

$\delta_{V_{i,t,d}}$ Voltage angle of node i at hour t of the day d in [°]

C_{bat} Total battery cost in [€]

C_{MPC} Total cost of the multiport converter in [€]

C_{oth} Cost of other additional equipment in [€]

C_T Total investment cost in [€]

E_{curt} Annual renewable generation curtailment in [%]

E_{ren} Annual renewable generation in [kWh]

$i_{i,k,t,d}$ Current of the line between nodes i, k at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

I_{ren} Annual income from renewable generation in [kWh]

k_{bat} Slope of the regression that relates variations of the payback time and battery cost in [p.u.]

k_{conv} Slope of the regression that relates variations of the payback time and converter cost in [p.u.]

$p_{buy-g,i,t,d}$ Active power bought from the main grid in [p.u.]

$p_{char-b,i,t,d}$ Active charging power of the battery b connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$p_{disch-b,i,t,d}$ Active discharging power of the battery b connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$p_{g,i,t,d}$ Active power provided by the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$p_{i,t,d}$ Total active power injected at node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$p_{load-i,t,d}$ Active power load in [p.u.]

$p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$ Active power exchanged by the multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$p_{sell-g,i,t,d}$ Active power sold to the main grid in [p.u.]

PBT Payback time respect an initial base configuration in [years]

$q_{b,i,t,d}$ Reactive power provided by the battery b connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$q_{g,i,t,d}$ Reactive power provided by the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$q_{i,t,d}$ Total reactive power injected at node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$q_{load-i,t,d}$ Reactive power load in [p.u.]

$q_{MG,i,t,d}$ Reactive power exchanged with the main grid in [p.u.]

$q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$ Reactive power exchanged by the multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$s_{n,MPC-k,i}$ Maximum apparent power of the multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i in [p.u.]

$SOC_{b,i,t,d}$ State of charge of the battery b connected to the node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

$v_{i,t,d}$ Voltage magnitude of node i at hour t of the day d in [p.u.]

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1 Introduction

The European Union has the objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions to be climate-neutral by 2050 [1]. To do so, the share of renewable energy and energy efficiency should increase. Precisely, the European Union is targeting 42.5 % of renewables by 2030 [2], and it is intended to continue growing. In this context, renewable generation is having a massive expansion in distribution level of the electrical grid, both at medium voltage (MV) and low voltage (LV). Additionally, due to the stochastic nature of renewable sources such as PV and wind power, it is needed a huge deployment of energy storage systems (ESS) to provide the overall system with flexibility, reliability and security [3].

The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) is transforming the conventional design and operation of the electrical grid. In particular, the high penetration of renewables is leading to a number of technical challenges related to overloads, voltage regulation, fault levels or power quality issues [4]. Solutions to increase the maximum amount of distributed energy resources (DER) that can be integrated into a distribution grid can be the construction of new lines, reinforcement of the grid with new equipment, demand management and storage systems.

In this situation, power electronics have an important role and an increasing presence in the system. In particular, voltage source converters (VSC) interconnect renewables such as wind or photovoltaic (PV) generation and battery energy storage (BESS) to the grid, but also provide active and reactive power control to reduce overloads and regulate voltages. The multiport converter (MPC) is presented as a general power electronics solution, which combines several terminals and functionalities.

In general, the lack of optimum design usually leads to systems which are oversized or not properly planned, and therefore with higher costs. Modern distribution systems are complex and complicated, as they can involve several energy sources, energy storage, management, and power electronics. Therefore their planning and analysis is a challenge [5]. Furthermore, their design should include sizing of the assets, optimal operation, and economic analysis of the system. In that sense, the models used for this purpose need to balance simplicity, accuracy, precision, and data granularity. Therefore, the most appropriate model will depend on the project complexity, assets considered, and data availability [6].

Furthermore, this thesis is developed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project named Distributed multiport converters for integration of renewables, storage systems and loads while enhancing performance and resiliency of modern distributed networks (iPlug) with grant agreement 101069770 [7]. This project aims to provide innovative technologies to overcome the challenges of integrating massive amounts of renewables in the LV and MV distribution grid and energy storage systems, as well as enhancing the usage of distribution networks and provide services. The author's contribution to the project is the development of a multiport converter (MPC) sizing methodology.

1.1 Objectives

The main objectives of this thesis are:

- Develop a multiport converter sizing methodology.
- Analyse the advantages of introducing multiport converters in the distribution grid.
- Apply the knowledge acquired in the Master's in Energy Engineering and the Master's in Industrial Engineering.

The specific objectives are:

- Review software used for planning and analysis of electrical networks.
- Develop an optimisation-based methodology to size multiport converters and provide a techno-economical analysis.
- Develop the software corresponding to the previous methodology.
- Find a case study where the multiport converter can be useful.
- Apply the methodology to the case study:
 - Perform a sensitivity analysis.
 - Compare the introduction of a multiport converter with other conventional options.
 - Analyse the performance of the system.

1.2 Scope

This thesis develops a methodology to size multiport converters and analyses how their introduction can improve distribution systems' performance. As a case study, this thesis focuses on systems with high penetration of renewable generation. Therefore, the MPC is used to increase renewable generation, but other services could be considered in future studies. Furthermore, this thesis consists only of simulations and no laboratory tests are performed.

It is important to ensure that the power system will remain stable when increasing the renewable generation and with the introduction of the multiport converter and the battery. However, stability issues have been kept out of the scope of this thesis and only steady state analysis is performed.

This work is mainly focused on the technical aspects of introducing a multiport converter in a distribution system, although an economic analysis is also required. Due to the workload of other more significant aspects, the economic parameters are mostly based on the bibliography. A sensitivity analysis of these parameters is performed to quantify the effect of their variability. Therefore, all economic results let to reach general conclusions, but their concrete values should be considered as illustrative.

Another important supposition is that the historical data of the loads and renewable sources represent a perfect forecast for the years studied. The electric loads are known to evolve with

the years, and the availability of renewable sources is uncertain by nature. Not considering this variability in a planning methodology, as presented in this thesis, is a significant scope limitation.

Moreover, other simplifications have been considered in the sizing optimisation due to computational requirements. In this sense, a computer with *Windows 11 Pro* operative system of 64-bit, Intel® Core *i7* @ 3.40GHz and 16.0 G RAM is used. It was aimed that the optimisation could be solved in less than one hour.

1.3 Structure

The report is structured as follows.

- Chapter 2 includes a literature review on multiport converters and software used for electric power systems simulation and optimisation, as well as an introduction to some concepts about optimisation.
- Chapter 3 presents the methodology developed in the thesis. Chapter 3.1 introduces how are selected the days of study from annual data. Chapter 3.2 presents a simple way to size the storage of a system based on specific requirements. Chapter 3.3 explains the optimisation model developed to size the multiport converter. Chapter 3.4 presents the software developed and the implementation of the optimisation model.
- Chapter 4 describes the case study in which the methodology is applied. Chapter 4.1 presents the network and the base data of the load and generation power profiles. Chapter 4.2 explains how the actual case study is built and the different scenarios that will be considered. Chapter 4.3 further explains the selection of the days of study from the case study annual data.
- Chapter 5 analyses the results. First, battery sizing results are explained in Chapter 5.1. Then, multiport converter sizing results are presented in Chapter 5.2, where a technological analysis is performed.
- Chapter 6 presents the costs of developing this thesis.
- Chapter 7 presents the planning of the thesis.
- Chapter 8 analyzes the environmental impact of developing this thesis.
- Chapter 9 analyzes the social and gender equality impact of this thesis.
- The conclusions and future work are presented at the end.

2 Theoretical background

This chapter explains further the context of the project while presenting a literature review on multiport converters. Also different software used for electric power systems simulation and optimisation are compared, and some basic optimisation concepts are explained.

2.1 Integration of renewables to the grid

As mentioned in Chapter 1, renewable energy is gradually increasing in the MV and LV distribution grid [1, 2]. In that context, the concept of active distribution network appears as a group of controllable loads and DERs [8]. Active distribution systems can involve several energy sources, energy storage, demand-side load management, and power electronics.

Nowadays, the most relevant distributed generation technologies are PV, solar thermal, wind, hydroelectric, biomass, geothermal, small-scale conventional generators, and combined heat and power (CHP). A modelling example of conventional power plants, PV and wind power plants, pumped-storage hydropower plants, and solar thermal power plants is presented in [9].

Energy storage is needed to balance demand and supply. This is especially important with renewable sources that provide an intermittent supply due to their stochastic nature. Furthermore, energy storage helps in the integration of PV and wind power by making them more flexible and increasing their usability, as it allows to store peak generation as energy reserves for on-peak supply. Batteries are also used as uninterruptible power supply (UPS) units in stand-alone applications and as a backup in case of power failure. Therefore, energy storage increases electric service reliability and security while decreasing operating costs and carbon dioxide emissions [10, 11].

Energy storage can reduce grid congestion, and therefore it can provide transmission and distribution grid benefits. On the one hand, it can postpone the construction of new lines, transformers, capacitor banks, substations or their subsequent upgrade. On the other hand, energy storage improves grid stability and power quality, resulting in a more efficient system. Specifically, batteries can provide power quality assurance, voltage support and control, frequency regulation and stability, load levelling, and peak shaving. Energy storage can also provide black start capability, renewable energy capacity firming, time-of-use shifting, and peak limiting [10, 11, 12].

Regarding the ESS, several technologies can provide different benefits according to their rated power and storage capacity. The main technologies used nowadays are pumped hydro storage (PHES), compressed air energy storage (CAES), batteries, flywheel energy storage (FES), supercapacitors, superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES), thermal energy storage (TES), hydrogen storage. Although, batteries have the widest application range [10, 11, 13]. Regarding the modelling of ESS, as with the generation assets, it will depend on the technology. For example, [13] provides some cost models for different storage technologies.

2.1.1 Multiport converter

Power electronics components have an important role in improving the operation of the distribution grid and are currently used. Particularly, VSC provides active and reactive power control, which allows reducing overloads and ensuring voltage regulation, and can operate as active filters. Moreover, renewable-based DERs and battery storage are connected to the grid through

VSCs. And direct current (DC) microgrids are embedded in the distribution alternating current (AC) grid through AC-DC converters. Also, other power electronics devices have been suggested for supporting the increase of renewable generation in the distribution grid [14].

Soft Open Points (SOP) are presented as a solution to connect and reconfigure feeders of the distribution grid. Where power controllability and firewall capacity against faults are the main advantages of SOP compared to a simple switch [15, 16, 17]. SOPs are usually based on a VSC back-to-back configuration [15, 17] with the possibility to connect storage in the DC link [18] or a multi-terminal configuration [19]. Also, other converter topologies are presented based on multilevel topologies [20] or matrix converters [21].

Solid State Transformers (SST) are another similar power electronics solution, the main purpose of which is to replace conventional transformers interconnecting different voltage levels (both low and medium voltage) and providing additional grid support functionalities [22]. Isolated options including a dual active bridge, i.e. DC-DC converter with high-frequency transformer, are usually selected in the literature [23], but also partially isolated or non-isolated options based on back-to-back configurations can be also considered [24].

The MPC can represent an improvement of the SOP concept combined with SST. The MPC considers the possibility of integrating multiple ports with AC and DC outputs, which could be used to introduce storage or DC loads, such as electric vehicle charging stations, between AC feeders or microgrids (Figure 1). Compared to the SOPs, the MPC is expected to provide additional services for the AC and DC systems using the support of battery storage, for example, frequency support. Moreover, the introduction of multiport converters improves flexibility and controllability, since power flows can be controlled to improve grid efficiency, provide grid services and prevent line and transformer overloads or excessive voltage variations. Multiport converters also improve resilience of distribution grids, as islanding operation and black-start can be ensured for specific areas of the distribution grid, and they can be distributed in different locations to increase grid reliability.

Figure 1: Example scheme of a multiport converter

In terms of power converter design, the MPC presents alternative options to back-to-back configurations that are expected to reduce cost and increase reliability. In general, the design and services of the MPC are different in LV and MV distribution grids, especially regarding the topologies considered. In LV applications, AC-DC converters can be combined in a common DC bus. While in MV applications, converters with multiwinding configurations are preferred to ensure galvanic isolation between the terminals connected through the converter [25].

In the iPlug project, several potential applications for the multiport converter are studied [7]. On the one hand, the MPC can provide distribution network support. In some case studies, the MPC interconnects two or more networks to accommodate better power management between them, especially when they have different voltage levels. Also, are of interest those MV and LV networks with potential for adoption of distributed renewable energy capacity. Related to this, the MPC can be used to connect neighbouring communities, enabling electricity exchange between microgrids to maximise system reliability and renewables utilisation factor. In this case, the MPC can also connect to the main power network, local generation and demand, and storage systems. Here, the MPC improves the communities' resiliency and could be used in regions where power outages frequently occur, such as rural locations or "conflict zones". On the other hand, MPC can also be used in buildings to interconnect local renewable systems with the distribution grid, support local energy storage systems and electric vehicles, and connection with DC appliances. The proposed system improves system efficiency by improving power management of distributed energy resources. The MPC also reduces renewable, EV and energy storage costs in comparison to conventional methods. Moreover, the MPC should also allow "system islanding" to operate as independently from the main network while experiencing faults in the main distribution system [26].

In this thesis, the utilization of multiport converters is focused on the contribution to facilitate a massive integration of distributed renewable generation while enabling the interconnection of multiple electrical grids and equipment in AC or DC and considers different voltage or frequency levels, number of phases or grounding schemes. The MPC implements an integrated solution combining the advantages of energy storage and other grid support equipment. Therefore, the overall number of power electronics can be reduced. Although the installation of multiport converters requires an additional investment in the distribution network, which must be compensated with the provided services explained before. Apart from the multiport converter, other options can be considered to increase the penetration of renewable sources such as adding regular energy storage systems, switches, new lines, and load management.

2.2 Design tools for power systems

Power systems planning tools have been widely studied in the literature [5, 6]. Several commercial software tools as well as new methodologies using mathematical models and various optimisation algorithms can be employed. These tools can have different characteristics and target users, as their applications can range from HV networks to microgrids. Therefore, a clear understanding of their features, capabilities, and limitations is needed to choose the most appropriate and apply it.

This chapter aims to take a closer look at the power systems design tools. However, those tools can be mainly separated into two types. On the one hand, there are those system planning and RES design tools, which focus on renewable resources and the characteristics of other assets, for example, HOMER [27]. On the other hand, there are tools which focus on the electrical grid specifications and analysis but keep the detailed modelling of other assets out of their scope. MATPOWER, GridCal, and PyPSA are examples of these tools.

MATPOWER is a Matlab package to solve steady-state power system simulation and optimisation problems, such as power flow (PF) and extensible optimal power flow (OPF). This tool models branches, generators, loads and shunt elements such as capacitors or inductors. The generator is modelled as an active and reactive power injection at a specific bus. Loads are de-

financed as constant values, but a dispatchable load can be modelled as a generator with negative power injection. MATPOWER includes AC and DC models to perform PF and OPF, but just for a single time period [28, 29, 30].

GridCal is an open-source power systems planning software. It is similar to MATPOWER but with a graphical user interface. GridCal performs DC PF, AC PF, DC OPF, and AC OPF with linear approximation. In contrast to MATPOWER, GridCal considers time series and simulates and optimises the whole time period. The model includes loads, shunts, generators, static generators and batteries that can be added to the buses. The connection between two buses can be modelled as a line, high-voltage direct current (HVDC), transformer, VSC, or unified power flow controller (UPFC) [31, 32, 33].

Python for Power System Analysis (PyPSA) is a Python toolbox to simulate and optimise modern electrical power and energy systems. In comparison with similar tools, PyPSA performs security-constrained linear OPF, and investment cost optimisation of the total energy system, in addition to static PF and linear OPF. Moreover, PyPSA can work with large networks and long time series. PyPSA enables to mesh AC and DC networks with converters, as well as coupling the electrical system with other energy carriers. This tool has models for standard types for lines and transformers, conventional dispatchable generators and links with unit commitment, generators with time-varying power availability, storage units with efficiency losses, and simple hydroelectricity with inflow and spillage. It also has basic components that enable to build more complicated assets such as CHP, heat pumps, resistive Power-to-Heat, Power-to-Gas, battery electric vehicles, and direct air capture [34, 35, 36]. Compared with PyPSA, the software developed in this thesis performs non-linear OPF and includes multiport converters.

2.3 Mathematical optimisation

As one objective of this thesis is to develop an optimisation-based methodology, this chapter is focused on explaining the main concepts of optimisation.

Mathematical optimisation is a branch of applied mathematics which is useful in many different fields. To optimise, an objective has to be identified first. This objective is a quantitative measure of the system performance which depends on certain system characteristics called variables. Examples of objectives can be costs or revenues, time, energy, or any set of quantities that can be expressed with a number. The optimisation goal is to find the values of the variables that maximise or minimise the objective. The variables are often limited or constrained somehow.

Modelling is the process that consists of the identification and definition of the objective, variables and constraints of the problem. This first step in the optimisation should balance simplicity and complexity, as too-complex models can be difficult to solve and too-simple ones may not represent properly the real system. After formulating the model, an optimisation algorithm is used to find its solution. Different algorithms can be applied according to the type of optimisation problem. Choosing an appropriate algorithm may determine the resolution speed and even finding or not a solution. A sensitivity analysis will reveal the solution sensitivity to changes in the model and data.

The mathematical formulation of an optimisation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n} \quad & f(\mathbf{x}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{G} \quad \text{Inequality constraints} \\ & \mathbf{h}_i(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{H} \quad \text{Equality constraints} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the vector of the variables, $f(\mathbf{x})$ is the scalar objective function to minimise, $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})$ are the constraints, which are scalar functions that define equations and inequalities that \mathbf{x} must satisfy, and \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{H} are sets of indices for the constraints.

2.3.1 Types of optimization problems

Optimisation problems can be classified according to their nature, the type of variables, objective functions and constraints. Deterministic optimisation problems are those in which the model is completely known. However, sometimes the model depends on unknown or uncertain quantities. Stochastic optimisation algorithms consider different possible scenarios and their estimated probability to approach this uncertainty and give solutions that optimise expected model performance. Other ways to deal with uncertain data include chance-constrained optimisation, where constraints have to be satisfied to a specific probability, and robust optimisation, where some constraints must be met for all possible values of the uncertain data [37].

In some problems, the optimisation variables can be only integer values. In these cases, the mathematical formulation also includes integrality constraints as $x_i \in \mathbb{Z}$ where \mathbb{Z} is the set of integers, including binary constraints as $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$. Optimisation problems that only have discrete variables are called integer programming problems, and if they contain both continuous and discrete variables they are called mixed-integer programming (MIP) problems. Usually, continuous optimisation problems are easier to solve due to the functions' smooth behaviour [37].

Constrained optimisation problems are those where constraints play an essential role in the model. On the other hand, unconstrained problems have $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{H} = \emptyset$. Reformulations of constrained optimisation problems where constraints are replaced by penalisation terms added to the objective function to discourage constraint violations can also lead to unconstrained problems. Linear programming (LP) problems are those where the objective function and all the constraints are linear functions. Non-linear programming (NLP) problems are those in which at least one of the constraints or the objective are nonlinear functions. Quadratic programming (QP) problems are a type of NLP with linear constraints and a quadratic objective function [38].

Moreover, problems may consider more than one objective function, which are called multi-objective optimisation problems. One way to assess this type of problem is to assign weights to each objective function according to its importance and optimise an objective function defined as the weighted sum of all the previous objective functions. In this case, it should be noted that the weighting factors will have a high influence on the solution. Another possible strategy is based on an iterative and hierarchical process, where the objective functions have to be ordered from the most important goal. In this case, the first step is to solve the optimisation for the most important goal while the other objective functions are expressed as inequality constraints with reasonable limiting values. The next step will be to replace the objective function for the next in the hierarchy and add a constraint so that the new solution can not be worse than the solution found in the previous step, and this step is repeated for all objective functions

2.3.2 Convexity and solutions

The convexity concept is important in optimisation [37]. A set $\mathcal{S} \in \mathbf{R}^n$ is convex if the line segment between any two points in \mathcal{S} lies entirely inside \mathcal{S} (Figure 2a), formally expressed as:

$$\forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathcal{S} : [\lambda \cdot x_1 + (1 - \lambda) \cdot x_2] \in \mathcal{S}, \quad \lambda \in [0, 1] \quad (2)$$

The function $f(x)$ is convex if its domain \mathcal{S} is a convex set and the line segment between any two points in the function is above the function plot between the two points (Figure 2b, formally expressed as:

$$\forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathcal{S} : f[\lambda \cdot x_1 + (1 - \lambda) \cdot x_2] \leq \lambda \cdot f(x_1) + (1 - \lambda) \cdot f(x_2), \quad \lambda \in [0, 1] \quad (3)$$

Alternatively, the function is concave if $-f(x)$ is convex. Convex programming problems are those in which the objective function is convex, the equality constraint functions are linear, and the inequality constraint functions are concave.

Figure 2: Set convexity (a) and convex function (b).

Regarding the solutions, an optimisation problem has both local and global solutions. A local solution is a point with a lower objective function than all other feasible nearby points, whereas a global solution is a point with the lowest objective function considering all feasible points (Figure 3). In convex programming problems, the local solution is also the global solution. In contrast, nonlinear problems usually have local solutions that are not global ones. Many algorithms for nonlinear optimisation problems search only a local solution which won't necessarily be a global one, as global solutions are difficult to find and identify for many problems [37].

Figure 3: Generic function with local and global solutions

In general, optimisation algorithms are iterative, meaning they begin with an initial value of the variables and move to better values until they terminate. The difference between algorithms lies in the strategy to move from one point to the next. Usually, the algorithms consider the values of the objective, the constraints, and their derivatives. The algorithms should also balance robustness to perform in a wide variety of problems and starting points, computer time and storage

efficiency, and solution accuracy [37]. Some examples of algorithms are interior point methods, numerical methods, branch-and-bound methods (especially used in integer programming problems), the Simplex method for LP problems, among others. These algorithms are applied in the form of software both open-source, such as HiGHS (LP, MIP and QP) [39] and IPOPT (large scale NLP) [40], and proprietary, such as GUROBI [41] and BARON [42] (mixed-integer nonlinear problems, MINLP).

3 Methodology

The methodology developed in this thesis has the main objective of sizing a multiport converter. Figure 4 shows a flowchart of the general methodology, where three main steps are considered: representative days selection, storage sizing, and multiport converter sizing.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the general methodology

As inputs, generation and demand profiles for a year and with hourly resolution are provided. The technical parameters of the grid and the assets contained in the system are also needed. Moreover, cost parameters of the grid reinforcements such as storage and several interconnection options must be provided, as well as the operation costs of the connection to the external grid. As a result, several economical and technical indicators are provided to evaluate the advantages of installing a multiport converter. These indicators can be also employed to compare different interconnection configurations.

This methodology has been specifically developed to study a multiport converter used to interconnect MV feeders with renewable generation and energy storage. Although it can be used also on other systems including MV or LV distribution networks, microgrids, and buildings.

The central part of this methodology is the multiport converter sizing, which consists of an optimisation problem. As mentioned before, the mathematical optimisation formulation will follow equation (1).

If the inputs were directly given to the optimisation problem, it would result in an optimisation that sized the storage and the multiport converter with a time horizon of one year. However,

this optimisation would be too complex and computationally infeasible to solve with the available resources. For this reason, the optimisation is divided into three steps, simplifying the optimisation problem.

The first step of the methodology is representative days selection. Although ideally a planning optimisation should consider a 1-year time horizon, the methodology proposed tries to reduce the amount of data by using the idea of clusters. Therefore, considering the inputs from the whole year, several representative days are selected.

The second step is storage sizing. If storage is included in the system, the required energy capacity and power should be defined in this step. It is assumed that batteries are used as a storage solution, but other options could be also considered. There are several methods to size batteries, and also they can be sized based on different requirements. In this case, the batteries are sized to ensure island operation.

In the last step, the multiport converter sizing is performed. An optimisation problem is developed, which will be later explained, but the input profiles consider only the representative days selected before. As a result, multiport converter size and optimal system operation are obtained, as well as some economical and technical indicators.

The following chapters explain in detail the methodology of the representative days' selection, storage sizing, and optimisation problem.

3.1 Representative days selection

Following the previous idea of reducing the amount of data, the optimisation will consider only specific days instead of the whole year. The input profiles regard annual demand and generation, which is supposed as PV and wind power. To select the representative days all those profiles and their interactions have to be considered. Although several clustering algorithms and software can be used, this chapter presents a self-developed methodology shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Flowchart of the representative days selection methodology

First, different levels of load, PV power availability and wind power availability have to be defined. To define the levels it should be analysed each profile to determine one or more representative magnitudes that describe the profile. The levels correspond to a range of values of these representative magnitudes so that there are both extremes and some middle values. The detailed definition of these levels depends on the case study, therefore it will be deeply explained

in Chapter 4.3.

Then, all possible combinations between power levels of different profiles are considered. Each of those combinations can be seen as a type of day, resulting in a quite long list. Afterwards, each day of the year is classified as one of those types according to its profiles. For each type of day, a weight w can be defined as equal to the percentage of days it contains over the total amount of days considered, which is 365 for one year.

Finally, the representative day types are those with percentages w higher than 2.5 %. From each of those day types, a single day is selected. The days selected are the representative days. At this step, it should be taken into account that the selected days must have different power profiles. It should be tried as well that the selected days are from different seasons and days of the week, and that they are around the middle value of their levels.

3.2 Storage sizing

As mentioned before, for this thesis the batteries are sized to ensure island operation. Therefore, in case the feeders are disconnected from the main grid, island operation must be ensured for a specific time period. In particular, the battery sizing is defined based on the power and energy required during the periods with a lack of generation in the system. The methodology used to size the storage is explained below, although other methodologies can also be considered.

In this step, hourly load and generation profiles for a year are employed, but grid constraints are not considered. First, the net power exchange for each h hour is defined as:

$$P_h = \sum_i P_{d-i,h} - P_{g-i,h} \quad \forall h \quad (4)$$

where $P_{d-i,h}$ and $P_{g-i,h}$ are the demand and generation powers for each node i .

Then, the net energy exchange for a period of H hours starting at hour t is defined as:

$$E_{H,t} = \sum_{h=t}^{t+H} P_h \quad (5)$$

When $E_{H,t}$ is positive the feeders require additional energy to supply the demand that must be provided by the storage. When $E_{H,t}$ is negative the feeders have a generation excess that can be used to charge the storage. In this expression, it will be needed the net power exchange of hours out of the year of data, for that reason it is supposed that the next year will have the same profile.

The battery sizing only considers periods where P_h and $E_{H,t}$ are positive. The battery power P_{bat0} and storage E_{st0} must cover all cases, and are expressed as:

$$P_{bat0} = \max(P_1, \dots, P_{N_h}) \quad (6)$$

$$E_{st0} = \max(E_{H,1}, \dots, E_{H,N_h}) \quad (7)$$

where $N_h = 8760$ is the number of hours in a year.

At this point, the battery is sized to be able to cover 100% of the cases, including the worst possible scenario. As a result, the battery could be excessively high and oversized in the majority

of situations. Then, a value between 90 and 100% is considered to reduce the battery size, i.e. the battery cost. Therefore, the battery power P_{bat} and storage required E_{st} are defined such that a percentage of the total number of cases with positive $E_{H,t}$ are covered. For example, if 90 % of cases are covered, means that the 10 % of cases which need a bigger battery to be able to operate in island mode won't be considered in the sizing.

Finally, the battery capacity E_{cap} is defined as:

$$E_{cap} = \frac{E_{st}}{DoD} \quad (8)$$

where DoD is the depth of discharge.

3.3 Multiport converter sizing optimisation

The nominal power of the multiport converter terminals is determined with an optimisation that considers hourly load and generation profiles and the grid constraints. As mentioned before, full-year optimisation has high computational requirements. Therefore, several representative days are considered. In that sense, the proposed optimisation considers separate submodels, one for each representative day. Each submodel will include all system components and their constraints. To combine all the submodels in the main optimisation model, some additional constraints are needed. On the one hand, the sizing variables must be common on all days. On the other hand, energetic variables and indicators that represent the whole year are estimated to be the weighted sum of the representative days selected.

Different elements can be included in the optimisation: the grid, generators, battery storage, and multiport converter. Each of those elements is modelled separately with a set of variables and constraints, and all the models are interconnected.

The objective function, variables and constraints of the optimisation are shown below.

3.3.1 Objective function

The multiport converter is introduced to improve feeders operation without an excessive additional cost. As the methodology aims to size the MPC, the optimisation will minimise the multiport converter cost while optimising other indicators that will depend on the case study. Moreover, some minor terms can also need to be considered in the objective function to obtain a correct optimisation performance.

This methodology can be applied to a wide range of scenarios. However, in this thesis, it is initially considered to be applied in scenarios with high penetration of renewable generation to explore the advantages of a multiport converter. In such scenarios, renewable generation is likely to be curtailed due to a limited line or transformer capacity. Therefore a multiport converter could be used to maximise the line and transformer capacity factor and reduce the generation curtailment. In this context, to avoid renewable energy curtailment, the income due to renewable generation is maximised for a period of 30 years, which is similar to the converter lifetime.

Additionally, depending on how the variables and their constraints are formulated, other terms may be added to the objective function. A usual reason for needing this term is to avoid using binary variables to relate two opposite variables.

Therefore, the optimisation will minimise the multiport converter cost and minimise generation curtailment, i.e. maximising feeders' operation income due to additional generation enabled by the multiport converter. As a result, the objective function can be expressed as:

$$[\min] C_{MPC} - I_{ren} \cdot t_{life} + other \quad (9)$$

where C_{MPC} is the multiport converter cost, I_{ren} is the annual income from renewable generation and t_{life} is a factor to weight the two main terms supposed as 30 years, which is similar to the multiport converter lifetime. The expressions of C_{MPC} and I_{ren} are presented in Chapter 3.3.5 and 3.3.6 respectively. $other$ represents the additional minor term that may be needed, which is formulated in Chapter 3.3.7.

3.3.2 Grid model

Grid variables are related to its operation. Therefore, they are defined for each electrical node i and for each hour t of the considered representative days d . Grid variables include active and reactive power injected ($p_{i,t,d}$ and $q_{i,t,d}$), voltage phase and magnitude ($\delta_{V_{i,t,d}}$ and $v_{i,t,d}$), and line current ($i_{i,k,t,d}$) between nodes i, k . All these variables are expressed per unit, except the phases, which are expressed in degrees.

The grid constraints are related to:

- Voltage magnitude limits:

$$v_{min,i} \leq v_{i,t,d} \leq v_{max,i} \quad (10)$$

where $v_{min,i}$ and $v_{max,i}$ are supposed as $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value.

- The main grid is supposed to be the slack. Therefore, the voltage magnitude and angle of the main grid node are fixed at 1 p.u. and 0° respectively, for all hours t and all days d .
- AC power flow equations to ensure active and reactive power balance:

$$p_{i,t,d} = v_{i,t,d} \cdot \sum_k v_{k,t,d} \cdot \left(G_{i,k} \cdot \cos(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) + B_{i,k} \cdot \sin(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) \right) \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (11)$$

$$q_{i,t,d} = v_{i,t,d} \cdot \sum_k v_{k,t,d} \cdot \left(G_{i,k} \cdot \sin(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) + B_{i,k} \cdot \cos(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) \right) \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (12)$$

where $G_{i,k}$ and $B_{i,k}$ are the real and imaginary part of the grid admittance matrix (Y_{bus}) at nodes i, k [43] expressed per unit.

- Line current limits. The current of each line is calculated and its maximum value is limited. The current can be expressed as (14), but this expression is reformulated as (15) to avoid complex numbers.

$$\underline{v}_{i,t,d} = v_{i,t,d} \cdot (\cos \delta_{V_{i,t,d}} + j \sin \delta_{V_{i,t,d}}) \quad (13)$$

$$\underline{i}_{i,k,t,d} = (\underline{v}_{i,t,d} - \underline{v}_{k,t,d}) \cdot \frac{1}{z_{i,k}} - \underline{v}_{i,t,d} \cdot \frac{y_{i,k}}{2} \quad (14)$$

$$i_{i,k,t,d}^2 = \frac{v_{i,t,d}^2 + v_{k,t,d}^2 - 2 \cdot v_{i,t,d} \cdot v_{k,t,d} \cdot \cos \delta_{V_{k,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{i,t,d}}}{z_{i,k}^2} + \frac{y_{i,k} \cdot v_{i,t,d}^2 \cdot \cos \delta_{z_{i,k}} + \delta_{y_{i,k}}}{z_{i,k}} - \frac{y_{i,k} \cdot v_{i,t,d} \cdot v_{k,t,d} \cdot \cos \delta_{y_{i,k}} + \delta_{V_{i,t,d}} + \delta_{z_{i,k}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}}{z_{i,k}} + \frac{y_{i,k}^2 \cdot v_{i,t,d}^2}{4} \quad \forall i, k, t, d \quad (15)$$

$$i_{i,k,t,d}^2 \leq i_{max-i,k}^2 \quad \forall i, k, t, d \quad (16)$$

where $i_{max-i,k}$ is the current limit of the line between nodes i, k , $z_{i,k}$ and $y_{i,k}$ are line impedance and admittance magnitude expressed per unit, and $\delta_{z_{i,k}}$ and $\delta_{y_{i,k}}$ are their respective phases expressed in degrees.

3.3.3 Generator model

The generators of this problem are supposed to be from renewable sources, meaning PV and wind power. PV and wind power variables are related to their operation, including active and reactive power generated ($p_{g,i,t,d}$ and $q_{g,i,t,d}$), which are defined for each generator g connected to the node i and for each hour t of the considered representative days d . All these variables are expressed per unit.

The generator constraints are related to:

- Generation curtailment. The active power provided by each renewable generator is positive and limited by the maximum available power from the generation profiles. Then, the active power generation limits are expressed as;

$$0 \leq p_{g,i,t,d} \leq p_{max-g,i,t,d} \quad \forall g, i, t, d \quad (17)$$

where $p_{max-g,i,t,d}$ is the maximum available power from the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d

- Generator current limits. As generators are connected to the grid through VSC, they can exchange reactive power. But the total power is limited by a maximum current, which can be expressed as:

$$p_{g,i,t,d}^2 + q_{g,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max-g,i})^2 \quad \forall g, i, t, d \quad (18)$$

$$i_{max-g,i} = \frac{s_{max-g,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall g, i \quad (19)$$

$$s_{max-g,i} = \frac{p_{n-g,i}}{PF_{g,i}} \quad \forall g, i \quad (20)$$

where v_{n-i} is the nominal voltage supposed as 1, $PF_{g,i}$ is the power factor supposed as 0.915 which corresponds to a reactive power minimum capability of $\pm 44\%$ (Figure 6) [44], and $p_{n-g,i}$ is the nominal active power of the generator.

3.3.4 Battery storage model

BESS variables are also related to the operation, as batteries are supposed to be sized previously to the optimisation. Therefore, BESS variables are defined for each battery b connected to the node i for each hour t of the considered representative days d . They include active charging and discharging powers ($p_{char-b,i,t,d}$ and $p_{disch-b,i,t,d}$), reactive power exchanged ($q_{b,i,t,d}$), and the state of charge ($SOC_{b,i,t,d}$). All these variables are expressed per unit.

The BEES constraints are related to:

- Charging and discharging power limits, which are expressed as:

$$0 \leq p_{char-b,i,t,d} \leq p_{n-b,i} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (21)$$

$$0 \leq p_{disch-b,i,t,d} \leq p_{n-b,i} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (22)$$

where $p_{n-b,i}$ is the nominal active power of the battery b connected to the node i .

- SOC limits, which are expressed as:

$$SOC_{min-b,i} \leq SOC_{b,i,t,d} \leq SOC_{max-b,i} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (23)$$

where $SOC_{min-b,i}$ and $SOC_{max-b,i}$ are minimum and maximum SOC values, supposed as 0.2 and 1 according to manufacturer recommendations [13].

- SOC calculation, which is expressed as:

$$SOC_{b,i,t,d} = SOC_{b,i,t-1,d} \cdot (1 - \tau_{bat}) + \left(p_{char-b,i,t,d} \cdot \eta_{char} + \frac{p_{disch-b,i,t,d}}{\eta_{disch}} \right) \cdot S_b \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{E_{cap-b,i}} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (24)$$

where τ_{bat} is the energy loss ratio supposed as 0.001 [13], η_{ch} and η_{disch} are the charging and discharging efficiencies both supposed as 0.9 [13], S_b is the base power of the system, and Δt is the calculation period, which is 1 h.

- Daily SOC level. The SOC must be the same at the beginning and the end of each representative day to ensure that the battery has a cycling operation. Moreover, the SOC at the beginning of the day is unknown. This can be expressed as:

$$SOC_{b,i,t=0,d} = SOC_{b,i,t=24,d} \quad \forall b, i, d \quad (25)$$

- Battery converter current limits. If the battery is directly connected to the multiport, the connection is in DC and this constraint is not applied. But if the battery is connected to the grid, a VSC is used. Therefore it can exchange reactive power with a limit of maximum current, which can be expressed as:

$$(p_{char-b,i,t,d} - p_{disch-b,i,t,d})^2 + q_{b,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max-b,i})^2 \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (26)$$

$$i_{max-b,i} = \frac{s_{max-b,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall b, i \quad (27)$$

$$s_{max-b,i} = \frac{p_{n-b,i}}{PF_{b,i}} \quad \forall b, i \quad (28)$$

where $PF_{b,i}$ is the power factor supposed as 0.915 which corresponds to a reactive power minimum capability of $\pm 44\%$ (Figure 6) [44].

3.3.5 Multiport converter model

Multiport converter variables are related to both the operation and sizing of the converter. Operation variables are defined for each multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i for each hour t of the considered representative days d . They include the active and reactive powers exchanged by the multiport converter terminal, $p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$ and $q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$. On the other hand, this sizing variable is the nominal power of each multiport converter terminal connected to the node i ($s_{n,MPC-k,i}$). This variable is expressed as the maximum apparent power considering all hourly powers exchanged by the converter terminal. All these variables are expressed per unit.

The multiport converter constraints are related to:

- Multiport converter power balance. This must be ensured considering active powers exchanged by each converter terminal, including if a centralised battery is introduced as an additional terminal of the MPC. Therefore, active power balance within a multiport converter is expressed as:

$$\sum_{k,i} p_{MPC-k,i,t,d} = 0 \quad \forall t, d \quad (29)$$

- Multiport current limits, which are expressed as:

$$p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}^2 + q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max,MPC-k,i})^2 \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (30)$$

$$i_{max,MPC-k,i} = \frac{s_{n,MPC-k,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall k, i \quad (31)$$

- Reactive power limits. According to IEEE Standard 1547 [44], energy storage DER should be capable of exchanging reactive power with a minimum capability of $\pm 44\%$ (Figure 6), which corresponds to a power factor of 0.915. As the multiport presented in this thesis is planned to work together with ESS, it has been limited the reactive power following the same capability curve. If this constraint was not considered, reactive power would increase a lot the multiport converter's nominal apparent power. Therefore, the reactive power limits are expressed as:

$$q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (32)$$

$$-q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (33)$$

- Cost of the multiport converter, expressed as:

$$C_{MPC} = \sum_{k,i} C_{conv-k} \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \cdot S_b \quad (34)$$

where C_{conv-k} is the unitary cost of the multiport converter terminal k , supposed as 150 €/kVA [13].

Figure 6: Reactive power capability of energy storage DER [44]

3.3.6 Technical and economic indicators

In addition to the previous models, some technical and economic indicators have been defined to analyse the results and set the objective function.

The technical indicators considered are:

- Annual renewable generation (E_{ren}) which is expressed as:

$$E_{ren} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{23} \sum_{g,i} p_{g,i,t,d} \cdot S_b \cdot \Delta t \quad (35)$$

where N_d is the number of representative days, w_d is the weight of each representative day in the year.

- Renewable generation curtailment (E_{curt}). Due to grid constraints or converter power limits, the generators may not produce as much energy as is available. The curtailment represents the percentage of renewable generation reduction with respect to the maximum available for a year. This can be expressed as:

$$E_{curt} = \frac{E_{ren-max} - E_{ren}}{E_{ren-max}} \cdot 100 \quad (36)$$

$$E_{ren-max} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{23} \sum_{g,i} p_{max-g,i,t,d} \cdot S_b \cdot \Delta t$$

The economic indicators considered are:

- Investment (C_T). This represents the cost of additional equipment installed in the feeders, which mainly considers multiport converter costs (C_{MPC}). Also, costs from batteries [13]

(C_{bat}) or other equipment (C_{oth}) can be included. Then, the total investment cost can be expressed as:

$$C_T = C_{MPC} + C_{bat} + C_{oth} \quad (37)$$

$$C_{baty} = \sum_k \left(S_{n,bat-k} \cdot C_{conv} + \frac{E_{cap-k}}{\eta_{ch} \cdot \eta_{disch}} \cdot C_{cap} \right) \quad (38)$$

where C_{conv} is the converter cost in €/kVA, C_{cap} is the energy storage cost in €/kWh.

- Annual income from renewable generation (I_{ren}), which is expressed as:

$$I_{ren} = C_{en} \cdot E_{ren} \quad (39)$$

where C_{en} is the average annual energy price in €/kWh.

- Payback time respect an initial base configuration (PBT). This is the period to recover the initial investment based on additional income from the feeders' operation. Then, the payback time is expressed as:

$$PBT = \frac{C_T}{C_{en} \cdot (E_{ren} - E_{ren-bc})} \quad (40)$$

where E_{ren-bc} is the annual renewable generation in the base configuration. This indicator is especially useful to compare multiport converter solutions or alternative interconnection configurations.

3.3.7 Other variables and constraints

Besides the model of each component, to build the system it is needed to connect the elements. In that sense, active and reactive power balance must be done, expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{i,t,d} = & -p_{load-i,t,d} + \sum_{MG} (p_{buy-MG,i,t,d} - p_{sell-MG,i,t,d}) + \sum_g p_{g,i,t,d} \\ & + \sum_b (p_{disch-b,i,t,d} + p_{char-b,i,t,d}) + \sum_k p_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \quad \forall i, t, d \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

$$q_{i,t,d} = -q_{load-i,t,d} + \sum_{MG} q_{MG,i,t,d} + \sum_g q_{g,i,t,d} - \sum_b q_{b,i,t,d} + \sum_k q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (42)$$

where, for each hour t of the considered representative day d , $p_{load-i,t,d}$ and $q_{load-i,t,d}$ are the active and reactive power load at node i , $p_{buy-g,i,t,d}$ and $p_{sell-g,i,t,d}$ are the active power bought and sold to the main grid MG connected to the node i , and $q_{MG,i,t,d}$ is the reactive power exchanged with the main grid MG connected to the node i .

Additionally, some terms need to be added to the objective function to obtain a correct optimisation performance. With the current optimisation, some mathematical solutions would not have physical sense. On the one hand, the battery cannot charge and discharge at the same time. These variables have been defined separately because of the efficiencies but they are opposite. On the other hand, the energy exchanged between the main grid and each feeder is also defined with two opposite variables, power bought and sold, which cannot occur at the same time. One way to solve this situation would be to relate the opposite variables with an auxiliary binary variable, but this will result in a high computational cost. Instead, it is decided to implement an equivalent in the objective function. The sum of the variable pairs is minimised to achieve

that when one variable has some value, its opposite will be 0. Moreover, to relate this term with the main optimisation objective it is required to apply some coefficient, so it will not affect the overall results. This coefficient is supposed as 0.00001. Therefore, the additional optimisation term can be expressed as:

$$other = 0.00001 \cdot (other_{BESS} + other_{MG}) \quad (43)$$

$$other_{BESS} = \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{b,i} \sum_{t=0}^{23} (p_{char-b,i,t,d} + p_{disch-b,i,t,d}) \quad (44)$$

$$other_{MG} = \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{MG,i} \sum_{t=0}^{23} (p_{buy-MG,i,t,d} - p_{sell-MG,i,t,d}) \quad (45)$$

3.4 Software implementation

In the development of this thesis, different software tools have been used. Representative days selection has been done quite manually in Excel, whereas storage sizing and results visualisation and analysis were first implemented in Matlab. On the other hand, multiport converter sizing optimisation has been performed in Python. Specifically, Pyomo library has been used to model the optimisation problem.

Pyomo is a Python-based, open-source optimisation modelling language [45, 46, 47]. Pyomo supports an object-oriented design for the definition of optimisation models. The main steps of the modelling process are: create the model and declare components, instantiate the model, apply solver, and analyse results. A Pyomo model consists of a group of modelling components, including index sets, symbolic parameters, decision variables, constraints, and objectives (to maximise or minimise). Pyomo supports a wide range of problem types, including LP and mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP). Solving these problems requires using commercial or open-source solvers (not all distributed with Pyomo) [45]. The multiport converter sizing optimisation is a NLP problem. Therefore, IPOPT solver [40] is used, which is an open-source software package that can deal with large-scale NLP problems. IPOPT implements an interior point line search filter method [40], and it is designed to exploit 1st derivative (gradient) and 2nd derivative (Hessian) information.

The Python program developed in this thesis has the structure shown in Figure 7 and 8. Where *Data.xlsx* contains all the inputs, the models are inside the *blocks* folder, and all files are called from the *main.py* script.

Figure 7: Optimisation program structure

Figure 8: Flowchart of the scripts

The inputs correspond to the case study definition and have to be introduced through Excel. *Data.xlsx* includes several sheets for each system component, as shown in Figure 9. Also, inputs in the form of time series are introduced in different sheets. The datasheets (Figure 9) include the following information:

- *General* sheet indicates the number of multiport converters considered and its lifetime, how time data are structured, and base power and impedance.
- *Bus* sheet includes the voltages and type of bus.
- *Lines* sheet indicates the buses that connect, its impedance and capacity.
- *Trafos* sheet indicates the buses that connect, its impedance and rated apparent power.
- *Loads* and *Renewables* sheets indicate the type of load, to which bus is connected, and how to calculate active and reactive power.
- *Load P TS*, *Load Q TS* and *Renewables TS* sheets include the time series of active load, reactive load, and active generation respectively.
- *Battery* sheet indicates to which bus is connected, rated power and storage, SOC limits, efficiencies and cost.
- *Main grid* sheet indicates the buses that are connected to the external grid.
- *MPC* sheet indicates the buses that correspond to the multiport converter terminals, which terminals correspond to the each MPC, and the cost of each terminal.
- *Weights* sheet indicates the weight of each day.

Figure 9: Inputs structure of Data.xlsx

After writing all the inputs, main.py has to be run. This file includes the main loop and starts calling *pre_processing.py*, then *pyomo_processing.py*, solves the optimisation, and finally it calls *post_processing.py*. *pre_processing.py* imports the inputs from *Data.xlsx* and stores them in a single data class, it also puts the time data in the format required by Pyomo. *pyomo_processing.py* defines the optimisation model with the sets, the main decision variables and the objective function. It also includes the optimisation of all the selected days by calling to *General.py* and using the *Block()* attribute of Pyomo. *post_processing.py* takes the optimisation results and saves them by writing *Results.xlsx*.

The detailed optimisation model is inside the *blocks* folder. Each system component is defined in a separate script with its corresponding variables, parameters and constraints for a certain time horizon. *General.py* has the optimisation model for a single day. This script calls the model of all system components, but also adds the relationship between the elements and defines general system parameters and constraints.

4 Case study

This chapter presents the case study used, from where is the data obtained, and how different scenarios are built. Also, the application of the methodology first step is detailed in this chapter.

4.1 Network and profiles

The case study is based on the European MV distribution network from the CIGRE Task Force C6.04.02 [48]. The feeder's nominal voltage is 20 kV and the system frequency is 50 Hz. The network configuration and parameters are the same as in the CIGRE benchmark model.

This benchmark network has two feeders (indicated as A and B in Figure 10) which are optionally interconnected with switches in three locations. In the original benchmark network, switch 1 is located between buses 8-14, switch 2 is between buses 6-7, and switch 3 is between buses 4-11. In this case, only the interconnection between buses 16-17 is considered with the possibility to employ a multiport converter instead of a switch, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Electrical scheme of case study with multiport converter

The network parameters considered for the lines and transformers are shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. It should be mentioned that line segment 13 will only be considered if the switch is closed. Also, line segments 14 and 15 will only be considered if there is a multiport converter. When considering the multiport converter, buses 16 and 17 are equivalent to its AC ports, and

the line segments between those buses and the feeders have in total the same length as the line segment of the original switch.

Table 1: Connections and line parameters

Line segment	Node from	Node to	$R'_{ph} [\Omega/\text{km}]$	$X'_{ph} [\Omega/\text{km}]$	$B'_{ph} [\mu\text{S}/\text{km}]$	$l [\text{km}]$
1	1	2	0.501	0.716	47.493	2.82
2	2	3	0.501	0.716	47.493	4.42
3	3	4	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.61
4	4	5	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.56
5	5	6	0.501	0.716	47.493	1.54
6	7	8	0.501	0.716	47.493	1.67
7	8	9	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.32
8	9	10	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.77
9	10	11	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.33
10	3	8	0.501	0.716	47.493	1.3
11	12	13	0.510	0.366	3.172	4.89
12	13	14	0.510	0.366	3.172	2.99
13	14	8	0.510	0.366	3.172	2
14	14	17	0.510	0.366	3.172	0.8
15	8	16	0.510	0.366	3.172	1.2

Table 2: Transformer parameters

Node from	Node to	Connection	$V_1 [\text{kV}]$	$V_2 [\text{kV}]$	$Z_{tr} \text{ to } V_2 \text{ side } [\Omega]$	$S_{rated} [\text{MVA}]$
15	1	3-ph Dyn1	110	20	0.016+j1.92	25
15	12	3-ph Dyn1	110	20	0.016+j1.92	25

The CIGRE benchmark model also has loads and DER, but for our case study, these data are not used. Instead, there have been searched more detailed load and generation profiles based on real data. For that purpose, it has been searched for a location which would already have some DER units.

Load profiles are defined based on load information from six nearby towns in central Catalonia, as shown in Figure 11: Igualada, Rubió, Òdena, Castellfollit del Boix, Aguilar de Segarra, and Els Prats de Rei. It has been extracted residential hourly consumption of each city for one year, specifically for 2019, using Datadis which is a database of the Spanish electrical demand [49]. Since the load information is only for active power, reactive power demand is also included considering a power factor of 0.97.

Figure 11: Location of load and generation profiles

Different loads are connected at each bus of the case study considering the load profile of the mentioned towns. In particular, the load profile of each town is considered as a base value, such that each node has a total load proportional to the base profile of a specific town. The loads of each node will be further explained in the next chapter. Figure 12 shows an example of the load profile of the towns for one week, where it can be seen that the towns have quite different profiles.

Figure 12: Demands during a week

Solar photovoltaic and wind power are considered as distributed generation of the system. Generation profiles are defined based on resource information around the area where the towns are located. The generation information is obtained for a year, specifically for 2019, from *Renewable.ninja* [50], which is a website tool to obtain PV and wind generation profiles in any location. In particular, hourly available power has been extracted for 1 kW of wind power and 1 kWp of PV power installed. It has been supposed that the power availability will be similar in the area, so a single profile of each source is obtained. Moreover, these profiles can also be considered as base values and scaled afterwards with different amounts of power installation. Therefore, the generation profiles are obtained for the installed power of each node, which will be detailed in the scenario building chapter.

Regarding the batteries, they can be distributed at each feeder or centralized as an additional multiport terminal. All batteries are sized using the methodology from Chapter 3.2. Its feeder is considered in each distributed battery, and the overall system is considered in the centralized battery.

4.2 Scenario building

Besides the original data, in order to put together all the previous information and make it work, it is needed to build the actual case study. This chapter focuses on how the load and generation units are distributed in the buses as shown in Figure 10.

Table 3 presents the load distribution in each node as a multiplicative factor of the towns' load profiles. This distribution is arbitrarily selected in order to have a comparable demand while ensuring that the grid structure is adequate.

Table 3: Load distribution

Node	Igualada	Rubió	Òdena	Castellfollit del Boix	Aguilar de Segarra	Els Prats de Rei
1	0	0	0	0	6	0
2	0	3	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	3
5	0	0	0	5	0	0
6	0	0	0	6	0	0
7	0	0	0.5	0	0	0
8	0	0	0.6	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	2
11	0	0	0	0	5	0
12	0.2	0	0	0	0	0
13	0.1	0	0	0	0	0
14	0.2	0	0	0	0	0

As this thesis is focused on multiport converters to facilitate the integration of renewables into the grid, it has been found that in order to ensure that the multiport is feasible, and that there appears some curtailment, it is required that there is a really high penetration of renewable generation in the system. However, the generation distribution may have an important impact on the results. Additionally, the conclusions of this thesis are aimed to be as general as possible. Therefore, it has been decided to study 3 different scenarios, which represent potential situations to evaluate the advantage of interconnecting feeders:

- Scenario 1. Similar solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind capacity power are installed in Feeders A and B.
- Scenario 2. Wind generation is mainly installed in Feeder A, while PV generation is mainly located in Feeder B.
- Scenario 3. Most of the generation capacity is installed in Feeder A.

Table 4 shows the generation distribution based on the installed capacity power for each scenario. The total PV and wind generation installed in all scenarios is approximately the same to ensure a fair comparison. Furthermore, both load and generation data were distributed arbitrarily along the network so that the scenarios would have grid problems such as overvoltages, undervoltages and lines saturation.

Table 4: Scenario definition based on generation distribution

Nodes	Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
	PV [MW _p]	Wind [MW]	PV [MW _p]	Wind [MW]	PV [MW _p]	Wind [MW]
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	34	46	4	46	40	56
4	34	0	4	0	40	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	50	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	2	0	52	0	40
10	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	20	0	0	0
13	60	54	60	4	18	16
14	0	0	30	0	0	0

Moreover, a number of configurations are defined based on MPC options, but also considering other possibilities, such as direct switch connection or different battery distributions. Three MPC options are considered: MPC without battery, MPC with converter-connected battery and MPC with direct-connected battery. This last option does not include a controllable terminal for the battery to reduce costs. The MPC configurations are compared to a base configuration without feeder interconnection and a configuration with a switch connection. Also, the introduction of distributed or centralised batteries is compared.

Then, eight configurations are defined based on the previous considerations:

- Ref: reference configuration with two separated feeders without batteries.
- DB: two separated feeders and distributed batteries, which are sized for island requirements.
- DB-S: feeders with direct switch connection and distributed batteries.
- DB-MPC: feeders with a two-terminal MPC connection and distributed batteries.
- CB-MPC3, CB-MPC3f and CB-MPC2: feeders with a three-terminal MPC connection and a centralised battery. In CB-MPC3, the battery is introduced as an additional controllable terminal of the MPC, and that third terminal is sized in the optimisation. In CB-MPC3f,

the battery is introduced as an additional controllable terminal of the MPC, but the third terminal has the same size as the battery's nominal power. In CB-MPC2, the battery is introduced as an additional terminal of the MPC, but with a direct connection to the DC bus.

- MPC: feeders with a two-terminal MPC connection without batteries, where the MPC acts as a soft open point.

Finally, a sensitivity analysis with the parameters of Table 5 is performed to provide a general conclusion. Scenarios with 25 % and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity are also analysed.

Table 5: Sensitivity analysis parameters

Parameters	Base value	Additional values
Island time for battery size	2 h	1, 3 h
Energy storage cost	750 €/kWh	650, 800 €/kWh
Converter cost	150 €/kVA	140, 160 €/kVA
Annual energy price	50 €/MWh	20, 100, 150 €/MWh

4.3 Representative days selection

Following the methodology in Chapter 3.1, the representative days have been selected.

The load profile trend is similar for different days, as during the night the load is low and there can appear some peaks during the day corresponding to dinner time and at first hour in the morning. Therefore, it has been supposed that a representative magnitude is the maximum load, which has been divided into 5 levels. For the PV power availability profile, most of the days have a similar profile since it is not so common to have shadows. Therefore, it has been supposed that the maximum power generation is a representative magnitude, which has been divided into 4 levels. On the other hand, the wind power availability profile is quite variable. Its uncertain nature makes that, specially on days with significant wind power, the high wind power can appear for most of the day or only during a few hours. Therefore it has been taken into account both the hourly maximum power generation and the total daily generation, and have been divided into different levels. Table 6 shows the different levels considered for each magnitude.

Table 6: Classification levels considered to select the representative days

max Load [MW]	max P_{PV} [$\frac{MW}{MW_p}$]	max P_{wind} [$\frac{MW}{MW_{installed}}$]	daily E_{wind} [$\frac{MWh}{MW_{installed}}$]
<14.5	<0.3	<0.2	<4
14.5-16.5	0.3-0.6	0.2-0.4	4-9
16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	9-14
21.5-26.5	>0.8	>0.7	>14
>26.5			

As a result, a total of 15 representative days are selected for the multiport converter sizing. Table 7 shows the days selected and the weight of their type. Table 8 shows the detailed levels of the representative day types.

Table 7: Representative days selected and their weights

Representative day	Calendar day	Weight [%]
1	January 8	4.1
2	January 24	2.7
3	February 15	4.4
4	February 16	2.5
5	March 4	2.5
6	April 10	18.1
7	May 3	4.1
8	June 25	5.8
9	July 4	6.8
10	August 11	9.6
11	August 19	3.6
12	September 15	2.5
13	October 18	3.0
14	December 23	2.5
15	December 27	2.5

Table 8: Representative days classification levels

Representative day	max Load [MW]	max P_{PV} [$\frac{MW}{MW_p}$]	max P_{wind} [$\frac{MW}{MW \text{ installed}}$]	daily E_{wind} [$\frac{MWh}{MW \text{ installed}}$]
1	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	4-9
2	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	>0.7	>14
3	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	<0.2	<4
4	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	<0.2	<4
5	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	>0.7	9-14
6	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	<4
7	16.5-21.5	0.3-0.6	<0.2	<4
8	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	9-14
9	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	<4
10	<14.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	<4
11	14.5-16.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	4-9
12	<14.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	9-14
13	16.5-21.5	0.3-0.6	0.2-0.4	<4
14	14.5-16.5	0.6-0.8	>0.7	9-14
15	14.5-16.5	0.6-0.8	<0.2	<4

Figure 13 shows the profiles of the representative days. And considering the different scenarios and feeders, Figure 14 is obtained. Where, in total, the average load is 20 MW and the average generation capacity is 45 MW.

Figure 13: Total demand (top), PV and wind power availability (bottom) on the representative days

Figure 14: Total demand and generation at each feeder and in total at the representative days for each scenario

5 Results and discussion

This chapter shows and analyses the results of applying the proposed methodology to the presented case study.

5.1 Battery sizing

The batteries are sized based on a requirement of island mode following the method presented in Chapter 3.2. In particular, the batteries are sized to cover a ratio of 99 % of the cases that can operate 2h in island mode. For example, Figure 15 shows the ratio of cases for scenario 2 and a centralised battery, which results in $E_{cap} = 48.27$ kWh and represents a battery capacity reduction of around 37 % compared to a ratio of 100 % of the cases. Table 9 summarises the energy capacity and active power required for the batteries in each scenario and considering distributed or centralised options. It is clear that sharing a centralised battery between the two feeders results in lower total energy capacity and power, especially in scenarios 2 and 3. For example, in Table 9b, the energy capacity of the centralized battery is 0.5 % less than the distributed one in scenario 1, while this reduction is 8.4 % in scenario 2 and 3.1 % in scenario 3.

Figure 15: Ratio of total battery capacity required to cover 2h in island mode for scenario 2 and centralised battery option

Table 9: Battery sizing results

(a) Battery size for 1h island mode

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.12	16.84	6.06	8.41	17.97	24.95
Scenario 2	11.27	15.65	8.63	12	17.97	24.95
Scenario 3	10.78	14.97	7.62	10.59	17.73	24.64

(b) Battery size for 2h island mode

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.12	33.39	6.06	16.49	17.97	49.67
Scenario 2	11.27	30.54	8.63	23.67	17.97	49.67
Scenario 3	10.78	29.41	7.62	20.9	17.73	48.74

(c) Battery size for 3h island mode

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.12	48.57	6.06	24.24	17.97	72.4
Scenario 2	11.27	44.65	8.63	35.12	17.97	72.4
Scenario 3	10.78	43.55	7.62	30.93	17.73	71.67

(d) Battery size for 2h island mode when installed generation is reduced 25 %

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.61	34.58	6.51	17.65	18.96	52.55
Scenario 2	12.10	32.53	8.78	24.25	19.04	52.55
Scenario 3	11.46	31.07	7.91	21.84	18.62	51.96

(e) Battery size for 2h island mode when installed generation is reduced 50 %

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	13.10	35.77	6.96	18.81	19.95	55.43
Scenario 2	12.93	34.52	8.93	24.83	20.11	55.43
Scenario 3	12.14	32.73	8.20	22.78	19.51	55.18

5.2 Multiport converter

This chapter shows the results related to the MPC size and analyses the performance of the system while comparing the multiport converter with other options.

It is important to mention that, as the optimisation problem is non-linear, it is most likely that the results obtained will be local optimums. Therefore there's no guarantee that no better results can be obtained applying the same optimisation problem.

5.2.1 Sizing

The results related to the MPC size are analysed for all the scenarios and compared among the different configuration options. In relation to the sensitivity analysis, all the parameters in Table 5 are considered, except for the energy storage cost. This is because this cost is not included in the objective function (9), i.e. the optimisation results are not affected.

Regarding the sizing results, the rated power of the MPC terminals has low variability in scenarios 2 and 3 (Figure 16a). The terminals without battery are sized based on the optimisation presented in Chapter 3.3 and the resulting rated power is around 25 MVA, which is the nominal power of the lines and transformers. This happens because the currents saturate the lines and transformers, which will be further explained in Chapter 5.2.2.

In general, the MPC appears when the revenues for energy generation are higher than the cost of the converters. In fact, adding 1 MVA in each MPC terminal would be economically feasible if the annual generation increase is at least 300 MWh. These numbers are just indicative of the ratio between the cost of the MPC and the revenues for energy in the lifetime of the converter, which can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\text{MPC price}}{\text{energy revenues}} = \frac{2 \cdot 150 \text{ €/kW}}{20 \text{ years} \cdot 50 \text{ €/MWh}} \cdot \frac{1000 \text{ kW}}{1 \text{ MW}} = \frac{300 \text{ MWh increased generation}}{1 \text{ MW in each MPC terminal}} \quad (46)$$

The terminal with a centralised battery can be sized based on the method in Chapter 3.2. In this case, the active power is around 18 MW, as shown in Table 9. But this terminal can also be sized in the optimisation presented in Chapter 3.3. When optimised, the size of this terminal is lower than the battery's nominal power (Figure 16b). For example, the optimized power is in the range of 7-14 MW whereas in Table 9 the power range is 17-19 MW. This happens because there is no requirement for islanding operation in the optimisation, so the battery from Table 9 is oversized for normal operation.

Figure 16: Boxplot of $S_{n,MPC-k}$ for terminals without battery (a) and the battery terminal (b) considering all scenarios, configurations, and sensitivity parameters of Table 5

In scenario 1, the rated power of the MPC terminals without battery has a lot of variability. Taking a closer look (Figure 17), the energy price seems the most sensitive parameter, followed by the network configuration. The MPC size decreases when the energy price is low, and it tends to 25 MVA when the energy price increases.

(a) Port A

(b) Port B

Figure 17: $S_{n,MPC-k}$ for terminals without battery in scenario 1 considering all configurations and sensitivity parameters of Table 5

However, the highest variability in MPC sizing is found when changing the generation installed capacity, which is shown in Figure 18. As a general trend, the rated power of the MPC terminals is reduced when the generation capacity is also reduced. This is very clear in scenarios 1 and 2, where the power may reach 0 making the multiport converter not a possible option to reduce renewable generation curtailment. In scenario 3, due to its generation distribution, the generation has to be reduced a lot to observe a MPC size reduction defined by the optimisation. The terminal with a centralised battery in the configuration CB-MPC3f does not follow this trend because its size is equal to the nominal power of the battery, which is higher with lower generation to be able to fulfil the islanded operation request.

(a) Scenario 1

(b) Scenario 2

(c) Scenario 3

Figure 18: $S_{n,MPC-k}$ for all terminals with different generation capacity

5.2.2 Operation analysis

Taking a closer look at the results regarding the operation of the system, it can be seen where the problems or limitations appear and how the multiport converter contributes to improve the system performance. For this analysis, the representative day 10 of scenario 2 has been chosen and CB-MPC3 configuration has been compared with the Reference one, base values of Table 5 have been considered. This case is an example, but similar results are observed in other days and scenarios.

In the Reference configuration, the voltage throughout the day is around 1 on most of the buses, while the currents saturate in all lines of feeder B and have a peak of around 15h in some lines of feeder A. For this reason, the multiport converter tends to have the same nominal power as the lines and transformers in this scenario and configuration, as the MPC tries to redistribute the currents. The multiport converter has a significant impact as the voltages tend to increase in most buses especially during the mid-day. However, an off-peak in the buses of feeder B is observed around 15h, as can be seen in Figure 19. Figure 20 shows that the currents also tend to increase during the mid-day with the introduction of the MPC, where more lines get saturated including the ones connecting to the main grid. However, the power factor at the main grid connection with the feeders is similar in the reference configuration and with the multiport, as seen in Figure 21.

Figure 19: Buses voltage of scenario 2 with configurations Ref and CB-MPC3 in representative day 10 considering the base values of Table 5

Figure 20: Lines current of scenario 2 with configurations Ref and CB-MPC3 in representative day 10 considering the base values of Table 5

Figure 21: Power factor of the feeders' connection to the main grid of scenario 2 with configurations Ref and CB-MPC3 in representative day 10 considering the base values of Table 5

In this case, the multiport converter is mostly exchanging active power between the feeders and the battery connected is charged during the mid-day hours. Figure 22 shows the power coming out of each MPC terminal, where it is seen that in addition to active power, the microgrid also exchanges reactive power, but in lower amounts comparatively. This figure also shows that the battery performs one full charge cycle along the day.

Figure 22: Multiport power exchange and battery SOC of scenario 2 with configuration CB-MPC3 in representative day 10 considering the base values of Table 5

Analysing the system at hour 13, Figures 23 and 24 clearly show that the lines of feeder B are saturated in the Reference configuration, with current equal to 1 pu highlighted in yellow, and this feeder is already injecting 25 MW to the main grid. Therefore, the renewable sources in feeder B are being curtailed, whereas in feeder A the system still has some capacity to integrate more resources. When the multiport converter is introduced, the saturations of feeder B continue and even the voltage of one bus reaches the upper limit. But in this case, feeder B is injecting 25 MW to the MPC, which also injects power to feeder A. The amount of power exchanged between the feeders is as much as possible, as in this case where the line connecting buses 2 and 3 gets saturated. As a result, feeder A increases the active power injection to the main grid by almost 8 MW. At this hour, the MPC terminal connected to feeder B is working at nominal power, while the terminal connected to feeder A is working at 49 % of the nominal power.

Figure 23: System power flow of scenario 2 with configuration Ref in representative day 10 and hour 13 considering the base values of Table 5

Figure 24: System power flow of scenario 2 with configuration CB-MPC3 in representative day 10 and hour 13 considering the base values of Table 5

5.2.3 Technical evaluation of MPC

The annual renewable generation presents significant variations depending on the scenarios, configuration options and battery size. Figure 25a shows the results considering the base values of Table 5, but equivalent results can be obtained for the additional values of the sensitivity analysis. It should be mentioned that low variability on the rated power of the MPC terminals, present in scenarios 2 and 3, will lead to limited effect of the parameter variations on the annual generation.

As expected, battery introduction improves the annual generation, with an increase of more than 5 % of DB compared to Ref, as seen in Figure 25b. Feeder interconnection with switch or MPC also contributes to the annual generation, especially in scenarios with unbalanced generation with increases of 15-20 % in scenario 2 and 25-30 % in scenario 3, as seen in Figure 25b. Annual generation increase is directly related to a curtailment reduction, as observed in Figure 26, since high penetration of renewable generation implies significant curtailment in all scenarios due to lines and transformers' saturation.

Figure 25: Annual generation (a) and Annual generation increase from Ref configuration (b) for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5

Figure 26: Curtailment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5

In addition, a comparison between battery and feeder interconnection options is shown in Figure 27 to understand which is the most convenient option in scenarios with high penetration of renewable generation. It is clear that when the generation is unbalanced (scenarios 2 and 3), feeder interconnection with switch or MPC (DB-S and DB-MPC options) presents a higher increase in annual generation compared to a battery capacity increase (1h and 3h island options). However, when the generation is uniformly distributed (scenario 1), increasing the battery capacity can have the same impact on annual generation as interconnections with switch or MPC. It should be also mentioned that the cost of battery capacity is significantly more expensive than the cost of interconnection equipment. Therefore, the interconnection options are preferred compared to increasing battery capacity.

Figure 27: Annual generation for each scenario comparing some configurations

5.2.4 Economic evaluation of MPC

The economic analysis presents the investment C_T and payback time PBT evaluation on the case study to further compare the different configuration options and understand when the MPC is a convenient solution.

Regarding the investment, battery cost represents a significant part of the total cost, while the switch cost can be almost neglected. Figure 28 shows the results considering the base values in Table 5, where the battery cost accounts for more than 80 %. It is observed that the configura-

tions with MPC and centralized battery (CB-MPC3, CB-MPC3f and CB-MPC2) show slightly lower battery costs in scenarios with unbalanced generation due to a lower energy capacity, as presented in Chapter 3.2.

Figure 28: Investment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5

Although investment is significantly high, benefits from the curtailment reduction of renewable generation must be considered to provide a complete economic evaluation. The payback time is used to consider both the investment and curtailment reduction contributions. Two different payback times are considered in the economic analysis: payback respect to Ref and payback respect to DB.

The payback time results respect to the Reference configuration conclude that scenarios with feeder interconnection are the options that can mainly provide reasonable times compared with the lifetime of the components. Figure 29 shows the results considering the base values in Table 5, where the payback time is lower than 20 years for all scenarios and configurations with feeder interconnections.

Figure 29: Payback respect to Ref for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5

If the payback time is evaluated considering that the distributed batteries are already in place, the results are not only economically feasible but also very attractive. Figure 30 shows the results considering the base values in Table 5, where the payback time is lower than 20 years for all

scenarios and in particular lower than 4 years for scenarios 2 and 3. Configurations with switch interconnection (DB-S) have a payback time almost equal to zero due to the low cost of the switch components. However, it should be mentioned that configurations with MPC provide higher operation flexibility compared to a simple switch interconnection. Then, their payback time could be further reduced if the contribution of additional grid services were considered in the economic analysis.

Figure 30: Payback respect to DB for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5

Equivalent result trends are obtained considering the additional values of the sensitivity analysis parameters, but are not shown for simplicity. Even when the sizing and annual renewable generation results are approximately independent of the cost and energy prize variations considered in Table 5, as commented before, the payback time is highly affected.

Then, the payback time respect to Ref is further analysed with expressions in relation to cost parameters and energy prize. Linear regressions are derived for the expressions of the cost parameters. In particular, the regressions are obtained with a coefficient of determination R^2 close to 1.

The impact of the battery cost variation on the payback time variation is expressed as:

$$\Delta PBT = k_{bat} \cdot \Delta C_{cap}$$

$$k_{bat} = \begin{cases} 0.81 - 0.91 & \text{if there is MPC} \\ 0.941 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

where ΔPBT and ΔC_{cap} are the percentage variations of the payback time and battery cost. In general, battery cost variations highly affect the payback, as observed from k_{bat} , which has different values depending on the configuration.

The impact of converter cost variation (for battery and MPC) on the payback time variation is expressed as:

$$\Delta PBT = k_{conv} \cdot \Delta C_{conv}$$

$$k_{conv} = \begin{cases} 0.059 & \text{if there is no MPC} \\ 0.9 - 1 & \text{if there is MPC but no batteries} \\ 0.12 - 0.19 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (48)$$

where ΔC_{conv} is the percentage variation of the converter cost. In this case, the converter cost has a low influence on the payback time, as observed from k_{conv} , except when the only element considered is the multiport.

When there is no MPC or its sizing is not affected by the annual energy price, then the total system cost remains invariable. In this case, annual energy price impact has been analysed based on an expression that can be directly derived from equation (40):

$$\Delta PBT = \frac{1}{1 + \Delta C_{en}} - 1 \quad (49)$$

where ΔC_{en} is the percentage variation of the annual energy price. Configurations with MPC of scenarios 2 and 3 have low sizing variability, therefore the energy price impact on them can be explained with small deviations from equation (40). On the other hand, configurations with MPC of scenario 1 have significant variability as explained in Chapter 5.2.1, therefore the energy price impact is significantly higher than shown in equation (49), especially when the energy price is reduced. Overall, it is clear that this price has a significant impact on the payback time.

5.2.5 Scenario with 25 % generation reduction

The initial scenario considers a significantly high penetration of renewable generation. A 25 % reduction of generation installed capacity is considered in this chapter in order to analyse the effect on the MPC sizing and performance results.

In this case, a larger battery is needed due to the islanding requirement of the battery sizing method, and the MPC size is already discussed in Chapter 5.2.1. As a consequence, the investment increases due to the larger battery cost (Figure 33). Annual generation and curtailment are reduced, as seen in Figures 31 and 32. Moreover, the curtailment is significantly lower than in the initial scenario, therefore differences in the annual generation between the configurations are less evident.

(a)

(b)

Figure 31: Annual generation (a) and Annual generation increase from Ref configuration (b) for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 32: Curtailment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 33: Investment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

The payback time presents a significant increase due to the reduction of income from the sold renewable energy and the increase in battery costs, as seen in Figure 34. In this case, only scenario 3 would be feasible in all interconnection configurations. While in scenarios 1 and 2, only the multiport acting as a soft open point without batteries in the system would have a payback time respect to Ref lower or similar to the lifetime of the converter. If the batteries were already in the system, the multiport would be economically feasible in almost all configurations, as shown in Figure 35. Sometimes, even reaching higher benefits with lower costs, because the centralized battery is smaller than the distributed one. In Figure 35, the configurations whose payback is not clearly seen is because it is almost 0 years.

Figure 34: Payback respect to Ref for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 35: Payback respect to DB for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

5.2.6 Scenario with 50 % generation reduction

The previous scenario still has significant penetration of renewable generation. A 50 % reduction of generation installed capacity is considered in this chapter in order to further analyse the effect on the MPC sizing and performance results.

This case follows the same trends explained in Chapter 5.2.5, but with more extreme values. The battery is even larger, and the investment is also higher (Figure 38). Although, the multiport converter tends to disappear in some scenarios and configurations. This is due to the almost nonexistent curtailment from the Ref configuration in scenarios 1 and 2 (Figure 37). In those cases, the annual generation has almost no variation between configurations (Figure 36), which leads to extremely high paybacks respect to Ref (Figure 39). On the other hand, scenario 3 shows some increases in annual generation when introducing batteries and/or interconnecting the feeders (Figure 36), but they are not enough to make the paybacks respect to Ref feasible (Figure 39).

Figure 36: Annual generation (a) and Annual generation increase from Ref configuration (b) for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 37: Curtailment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 38: Investment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity

In fact, the payback respect to the Reference configuration only approaches the feasibility region with the MPC configuration without any battery (Figure 39). Scenario 1 does not have a multiport converter without battery, as its size would be zero, scenario 3 would have a payback of around 5 years, and the payback of scenario 2 is 21 years, similar to the lifetime of the converter (20-25 years).

Figure 39: Payback respect to Ref for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity

The payback respect to DB configuration is a bit harder to interpret. Figure 40 shows that scenario 1 would only be feasible with distributed batteries and some interconnection. Configuration CB-MPC3f is not shown for scenario 1 because the generation is lower than with distributed batteries and the cost is higher, so payback would be infinite. In scenario 3 all configurations are feasible, and in scenario 2 the only unfeasible configuration is the multiport converter with distributed batteries.

Figure 40: Payback respect to DB for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 5 and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity

To conclude, the MPC application in this case study is only feasible for scenarios with high generation or if the generation is unbalanced between feeders and the batteries are assumed to be initially installed in the system.

6 Economic assessment

This chapter presents the budget of this thesis, which accounts for human resources, equipment and software used.

The human resources costs refer to the labour costs related to the time spent on this thesis. Although the results of this thesis would not have been achieved without the work done previous to the master's thesis enrolment, this budget will consider only the expected time dedication. This thesis is equivalent to 42 ECTS, therefore labour costs correspond to a single person working 1050 hours. This work is supposed to be paid as 15 €/h, resulting in 15750 €.

Regarding the equipment cost, the thesis has been developed using a personal laptop. It is supposed that the computer is amortised in 5 years, and it has been used for 7 months.

For the software, Python and the optimisation solver are open-source, therefore they have no cost. On the other hand, MATLAB was also used. MATLAB and Simulink Student Suite license has a cost of 68 €, and the standard MATLAB license is 860 €, but the UPC provides a free academic license to their students. Moreover, the parts of this thesis developed in MATLAB could be done with open-source software, but it was decided to take advantage of previous work that was already written in MATLAB. For these reasons, software cost can be supposed as 0 €.

Additionally, the energy cost should be addressed. Considering that the laptop requires 65 W and it is used during 1200 h, it has consumed 78 kWh. Assuming that the mean electricity price during the thesis development is 0.15 €/kWh, the total energy cost is 11.7 €.

Finally, the total cost of this thesis is 16761.74 €, as can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10: Thesis budget

Concept	Units	Unit cost	Cost	Amortisation
Human resources	1050 h	15 €/h	15750 €	
Equipment	1	1000 €	1000 €	100 €
Software			0 €	
Energy	78 kWh	0.15 €/kWh	11.7 €	
Total			16761.7 €	

7 Planning

This thesis officially started in July 2023, although the results presented would not have been achieved without previous work. The methodology proposed started to be developed in November 2020 in the framework of the ERA-Net Smart Energy Systems project called Cross-Sectoral Energy Control through Interconnected Microgrids by Multiport Converter with reference number 91620. During three years, several versions of the multiport converter sizing methodology were developed and improved, also using different software and other case studies. During the last months, the final and proposed methodology was developed.

Table 11 shows the thesis Gantt with the parts developed from July 2023 to January 2024.

Table 11: Thesis Gantt diagram

Tasks	2023						2024
	07	08	09	10	11	12	01
Literature review							
Optimization modelling							
Case study definition							
Results obtention							
Results analysis							
Report writing							

8 Environmental assessment

This chapter presents the environmental impact of developing this thesis. This project mainly comprises software development and application to a case study, therefore the only material needed is a computer. For that reason, the emissions associated with the thesis are related to electric consumption and the equivalent emissions of having a laptop.

In Spain, the average emissions factor in the period from July 2023 to January 2024 has been 0.125 t CO₂ eq./MWh [51], as can be seen in Figure 41. As mentioned in Chapter 6, the laptop has consumed 78 kWh, therefore the emissions related to the electric consumption are 9.75 kg CO₂ eq.

Figure 41: Emissions and emission factor of CO₂ eq. of the generation in Spain [51]

Additionally to the energy consumption, having a laptop generates other indirect emissions related to its manufacture, transport and recycling. The analysis of the equivalent emissions related to all these stages is called Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). According to [52], the LCA of a laptop with similar characteristics as the one used in this thesis has a global warming potential of 146.8 kg CO₂ eq. where the manufacturing phase represents 109.9 kg CO₂ eq. and the transport 13.6 kg CO₂ eq., while the recycling at the end of life contributes to reducing the emissions 11.7 kg CO₂ eq. and it was considered a lifetime of 5 years. With this data, it can be estimated that the equivalent emissions of the LCA excluding the use stage are around 13.05 kg CO₂ eq.

Therefore, as can be seen in Table 12, the total emissions of this thesis are 22.79 kg CO₂ eq.

Table 12: Thesis emissions

Concept	Emissions [kg CO ₂ eq.]
Manufacture	12.82
Transport	1.59
Energy consumption	9.75
End of life	-1.37
Total	22.79

9 Social and gender equality assessment

This chapter presents the social impact of this thesis. Moreover, gender equality is separately analysed in both the thesis development and its social impact.

This project proposes a new technology to improve electric systems' performance. Specifically, a multiport converter is studied to increase the renewable energy penetration in the system. Therefore, regarding the Sustainable Development Goals [53], this work is related to:

- 7) Affordable and clean energy
 - 7.1) By 2030, ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern energy services.
 - 7.2) By 2030, increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix.
 - 7.A) By 2030, enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology.
- 9) Industries, innovation and infrastructure
 - 9.1) Develop quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure, including regional and transborder infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all.
 - 9.5) Enhance scientific research, upgrade the technological capabilities of industrial sectors in all countries, in particular developing countries, including, by 2030, encouraging innovation and substantially increasing the number of research and development workers per 1 million people and public and private research and development spending.

Adding multiport converters to the distribution grid will have a direct impact on the electrical system. Therefore, it is expected to have the same impact on all people regardless of their gender, race or other identities. Moreover, electricity costs are expected to be reduced with the increase of renewable sources, therefore making electricity more accessible. For that reason, this project can provide significant benefits to vulnerable groups.

On the other hand, increasing renewable energy penetration is one pillar of the energy transition as renewable energies do not emit greenhouse gases and help in the energy system's decarbonisation. It also mitigates climate change, which has several negative effects on the environment, human health and causes migrations. Additionally, as renewable energy is quite accessible, it has the potential to improve energy democratisation.

The contributions of this thesis can interest several companies in the electrical sector, from power electronics and battery manufacturers to distribution system operators, as well as microgrids and energy communities. In the iPlug project, under which this thesis is developed, there are Estabanell y Pahisa Energia and Infraestructures de la Generalitat de Catalunya as partners. Moreover, it is expected to publish a journal paper with the thesis contributions, which will

also benefit the research community.

Regarding gender equality in the thesis development, it should be considered that electrical engineering is a predominantly male environment. The research team in the iPlug project there's around 20 % of women representation. However, the team is promoting gender equality. As this thesis is developed by a woman, it contributes to the team and research with a different perspective. Furthermore, it promotes that more women join the field while showing what they can be capable of.

Conclusions

This thesis analysed the multiport converter as a potential solution to reduce generation curtailment in distribution grids with a high penetration of renewables. A general methodology was presented to size the required multiport converter based on an optimisation problem with electrical constraints. This methodology also provides technical and economic indicators for a complete evaluation of the multiport converter integration.

A case study inspired by the medium voltage CIGRE benchmark network was considered, where the general methodology was validated to size a three-terminal multiport converter with and without battery terminals. The results concluded that in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders, the rated power of the multiport converter terminals used to exchange power between different feeders was sized with a relatively constant value similar to the nominal power of the system. Whereas in scenarios with balanced distributed generation in the feeders, the size of the rated power of the multiport converter terminals was more dependent on the interconnection configuration and economic parameters.

This case study was also used to compare the multiport converter solution to alternative configurations with separated batteries and a simple switch interconnection. As a general conclusion, the results showed that the multiport converter provides clear advantages and is economically viable. In particular, the multiport converter can reduce power curtailment in equivalent terms or even better than battery solutions, especially in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders. From an economical point of view, all scenarios are feasible to install a multiport converter as long as the penetration of renewables is high. Different renewable penetrations were also compared. If renewable generation capacity is reduced, scenarios with unbalanced generation are the most economically feasible. However, scenarios with balanced generation are complicated to be considered unless batteries are initially installed in the feeders.

In general, for all scenarios, a multiport converter with a centralised battery is the best option. Configuration with a switch interconnection could provide similar economical results compared to the multiport converter options. However, the multiport converter has improvement margin since additional grid support services can be provided and are not evaluated in this thesis.

Future work

This thesis had a limited time and scope, but there are things to improve and the project will continue for some years. Further work on this topic can include:

- Consider other battery sizing methodologies.
- Planning methodologies usually consider one or several years. This thesis proposes a methodology to consider a few days instead, but other clustering algorithms or simplification methodologies can be considered to reduce the amount of data and speed up the optimisation.
- The optimisation of battery and MPC location.
- Consider other functionalities and economical benefits of the multiport converter.

- Improvement of the software regarding solver time and finding global solutions. As due to the solver used and the problem being non-linear, the results shown in this thesis are probably local optimums.
- Consider battery degradation and ageing in the methodology.
- Consider forecast uncertainties of the loads and resource availability in the optimisation.

Additionally, a journal paper with the thesis contributions is expected to be published.

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